

Giant Uterine Fibroid Expelled Through the Cervix: A Case Report and Review of the Literature

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Abstract

Background: Giant uterine fibroids expelled through the cervix are rare. They usually measure less than 3–4 cm and may cause dyspareunia, menorrhagia, and sometimes infection. They are prone to necrosis or superinfection, and management is essentially surgical.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 45-year-old nulliparous single woman who presented with a large mass expelled through the cervix and exteriorized through the vulva, soft in consistency, bleeding on contact and friction, measuring 35 × 12 cm. She reported pelvic pain and heaviness evolving for one year. MRI suggested a cervical myoma. Vaginal myomectomy was performed. Histology confirmed a leiomyoma. Postoperative course was uneventful.

Conclusion: Giant cervical leiomyomas are rare but may present with significant clinical symptoms. MRI plays a crucial role in diagnosis. Surgical removal remains the treatment of choice with good prognosis.

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Introduction

Uterine fibroids are the most common benign tumors of the uterus, affecting up to 50% of Caucasian women and 80% of Afro-Caribbean women over the age of 30. They are symptomatic in only one-third of cases, often earlier in Afro-Caribbean women. [1] Age and ethnicity are important prognostic factors [2]. The incidence increases with age until menopause [3,4,5]. Multiparity is considered protective, while the role of oral contraception remains controversial.

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Fibroids are mostly multiple (98%), localized in the uterine corpus, and only 3% occur in the cervix. Cervical fibroids are rare (<1%) [6]. Their topography determines clinical symptoms and guides management. Imaging, especially ultrasound and MRI, are crucial for diagnosis and pre-therapeutic assessment. Surgery remains the mainstay of treatment for symptomatic and exteriorized fibroids.

We report here a rare case of a giant submucosal leiomyoma expelled through the cervix.

Case Presentation

A 45-year-old single, nulliparous woman presented with a large, reddish, fleshy mass expelled through the cervix and protruding beyond the vulva, associated with pelvic pain and abnormal vaginal bleeding. She had a one-year history of intermittent pelvic pain, later followed by menorrhagia. Six months later, she developed a rapidly enlarging mass protruding into the vulvar region, with pelvic heaviness, constipation, pollakiuria, and dysuria. She had no personal or family history of major diseases or cancer.

On general examination, she was anemic, with moderate general condition, normal BMI (22 kg/m²), and signs of depression. Abdominal examination revealed a sub-umbilical bulge with diffuse tenderness. Vaginal examination showed a large, soft, violaceous mass (35 × 12 cm) exteriorized through the vulva, bleeding on contact and friction. (Figure 1) Vaginal and

rectal examinations were difficult due to the mass filling the vaginal cavity.

Figure 1: Masse Delivered by the Cervix

Pelvic MRI demonstrated a large intrauterine mass originating from the posterior wall of the endometrium, extending into the endocervical canal and vagina, measuring 370 × 158 × 125 mm, without signs of invasion.

Surgical management consisted of vaginal myomectomy under general anesthesia. Tumorectomy was performed by progressive morcellation until complete removal. The necrotic mass measured 23 × 16 cm. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Operating Piece

Histopathological examination confirmed a benign leiomyoma. The postoperative course was uneventful.

Discussion

Submucosal cervical leiomyomas expelled through the cervix are extremely rare. They usually measure only a few centimeters, [1, 2], whereas in our case the mass exceeded 35 cm. Clinical manifestations are dominated by pelvic pain, menorrhagia, pelvic pressure, and compression symptoms such as urinary or digestive disturbances [8]. Delayed diagnosis, as in our patient, often results from sociocultural factors and may explain the exceptional size.

The etiopathogenesis of fibroids remains uncertain, though hormonal (estrogen and progesterone), genetic, and growth factor-related theories prevail.

Imaging, especially MRI, is the gold standard for diagnosis and surgical planning. [7-10].

Management of cervical leiomyomas is primarily surgical, as medical therapy is less effective than in corporal locations. Surgical techniques include myomectomy via torsion of the pedicle or progressive morcellation. Histology is essential to confirm the benign nature of the lesion. Prognosis is favorable after complete excision.

Our case highlights the diagnostic challenges and the effectiveness of vaginal surgical management in giant cervical fibroids.

Conclusion

Giant cervical leiomyomas are rare but clinically significant due to their size and symptoms. They should be considered in cases of large vaginal masses. MRI plays a decisive role in diagnosis. Surgical excision through vaginal myomectomy is the treatment of choice, with favorable outcomes.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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